

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GEBREMICHAEL****FIRST NAME: SHEWAYIREF****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Presenting someone else's ideas or work as own, with or without that person's consent, by incorporating it into own work without giving it due credit is known as:

- Plagiarism.**¹
- Copywriting.
- Paraphrasing.
- Citation.

2. The verbal and visual presentation of ideas is today's most widely used and acceptable means of Research findings communication. Using the most preferred graphics or

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University), 34.

visual representation magnifies one's writer's thoughts and communicates with the readers. Which of the following is helpful to present verbal and visual presentations?

Tables and figures.²

Abstract.

Conclusion and recommendation.

Conceptual framework.

3. Which of the following is true about the spirit of the research?

Research can be a personal claim or suggestion.

Research is a way of communicating scientific evidence to others based on the principles that shape public evidence and evidence-based belief.³

Paraphrasing is one way to avoid plagiarism and does not need acknowledgment of the original author.

If the author has enough knowledge, he/she can do a scientific investigation without a literature review.

4. What are the main reasons to cite other sources?

To get credit.⁴

To minimize the budget.

To save time.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

³ Ibid., 137.

⁴ Ibid., 139.

- To decrease human resources.
5. When using citations, there are requirements. We have to fulfill those requirements to include sources in our paper or research work and the information that we provide in the paper. The required knowledge of cited material is:
- Who wrote, edited, or translated?**⁵
- The level of education of the writer.
- The number of persons who read the material.
- The study area.
6. A research section that will be presented in clear narrative form using relevant verbatim; the narrative data are connected and synthesized through substantive explanatory text, and visual displays is called:
- Methodology and research approach.
- Analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings.
- Findings.**⁶
- Conclusion and recommendation.
7. Which of the following countries are the current member states of the European Union?
- Germany, Israel, Denmark, and the United States.

⁵ Ibid., 141.

⁶ Ibid., 83.

- South Africa, Malta, Netherlands, and Russia.
 - Austria, Germany, Denmark, and France.**⁷
 - Russia, Turkey, Belgium, and India.
8. A research proposal is:
- A document used in business to solicit contracts.
 - A well-thought-out written action plan.**⁸
 - A research document presenting the findings of the research.
 - An action plan for the presentation of business ideas.
9. What does "Achieve alignment throughout the dissertation" mean?
- For the study to be methodologically sound, numerous key elements and concepts must be aligned and consistent throughout the dissertation.**⁹
 - Research problem, research approach, purpose, research questions, methodology and methods, literature review, conceptual framework, design and data analysis, study findings, interpretations, and conclusions all of the dissertation sections alignment is not necessary.
 - Alignment is needed for qualitative research, not for quantitative research methods.

⁷ European Commission. 2021. *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (Eighth edition: January 2016), 73.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 202.

⁹ Ibid., 237-239.

- The research study's components should be a collection of fragmented or isolated parts.

10. According to the WHO style guide, how are dates formatted?

- Day Month, Year
- Month-Day-Year
- Day-Month (in number)-Year
- Day Month (spelt in full) Year.**¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

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World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual*. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 1993.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Editorial Style Manual* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 1993), 52.

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